

Science

A STUDY ABOUT CAREER TRANSITION RESOURCES IN CORPORATE SECTOR IN INDIA

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Abstract

Career satisfaction is important for happiness of working persons, their family and closely attached persons. A person satisfied with his work provides happiness to others and guide them to follow his career path. If a person is not satisfied with work profile or field, then he needs career transition. Generally, such cases have been found in corporate sector in India. Proper guidance required to take right decision for career transition and work satisfaction. Present study is focused on finding of reasons and resources of career transition in India.

Keywords: Career Transition; Resources.

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1. Introduction

At present, a traditional linear career is unlikely to hold for the majority of employees. Each year, millions of people make an internal shift, reaching a point where they are ready to explore a new career. Transitioning may be to completely new career or new sector. It may bring into a leadership position. Sometimes career transition requires changing in work profile. Some persons transit career for development of new skills. Depending on the education requirements, the transition can sometimes take more time.

Generally, career transition process is adopted by them who are unsatisfied with their current careers, or who find that their skills are becoming outdated. Colleges and universities, job service agencies, private companies, and even some employers are all ready to help workers by offering job training, tools for job searching, and tips for interviewing and writing effective résumés and cover letters. Resources are also available for workers transitioning into retirement or for those who are considering starting a small business.

In previous generation, most people spent their adult lives working for a single company and expected to remain at that company until retirement. The workplace has become rapidly changing environment. In the wake of downsizing, restructuring, corporate takeovers, and outsourcing, jobs

that were once believed to offer lifelong job security no longer have such guarantees. Because of the volatile job market, many adults have had to either voluntarily or involuntarily reevaluate their careers. For some, this can be a time of opportunity.

There are many resources to help working persons to acquire the skills and knowledge needed to begin a new career. Some of these resources are offered by government, social service agencies, some are available through colleges and universities in the form of education and other support services, some come in the form of partnerships, and some are even offered by employers.

Job service agencies are one resource for adults considering a career change. Many now have websites that anyone can access and have links to local newspapers, employer websites, job postings, labor market information, and other resources. These agencies advertise state and central government as well as local job openings and update their listings daily. They also offer computers with software packages that can help clients create résumés and cover letters, as well as internet access so clients can search online job postings. Career centers also help adults who are preparing for retirement but would like to continue working after retirement.

2. Objective

- Finding of career transition strength in corporate sector in India.
- Finding of reasons of career transitions among working persons of corporate sector in India.
- Finding of resources of career transitions for working persons of corporate sector in India.

3. Hypothesis

- 1) There is no significant strength of career transition cases in corporate sector in India.
- 2) There is no significant reason of career transitions among working persons of corporate sector in India.
- 3) There is no significant resource of career transitions for working persons of corporate sector in India.

4. Methodology

Descriptive survey method was implemented for present study. 400 working persons of age 26 - 55 years were randomly selected as sample. 50% male and 50% female were incorporated in all age groups. Sample was classified age wise into 4 groups as 26-35, 36-45, 46-55 and 56-65 years. They were interviewed using self-prepared questionnaire regarding career transition. Collected data was tabulated and analyzed using percentile tool.

5. Finding and Analysis

Table 1: Strength of Career Transition Cases in Corporate Sector in India

Gender	Age Group	No. of Career Transition Cases (%)
Male	26-35 yr	59
	36-45 yr	42

	46-55 yr	31
	56-65 yr	12
Female	26-35 yr	52
	36-45 yr	41
	46-55 yr	24
	56-65 yr	9

Chart 1: Strength of Career Transition Cases in Corporate Sector in India

Table 2: Status of Reasons of Career Transition

Gender	Reasons of Career Transition	No. of Persons %			
		Age Group			
		26-35 yr	36-45 yr	46-55 yr	56-65 yr
Male	Salary	34	31	29	23
	Working Environment	14	12	11	13
	Work Place Distance	9	13	14	17
	Uncomfortable	15	11	11	10
Female	Managerial Problems	9	11	12	12
	Lack of Promotion	19	22	23	25
	Salary	31	29	28	24
	Working Environment	16	14	13	11
Female	Work Place Distance	11	13	16	19
	Uncomfortable	14	12	10	9
	Managerial Problems	12	14	14	21
	Lack of Promotion	16	18	19	16

Chart 2: Status of Reasons of Career Transition

Table 3: Status of Resources of Career Transition

Gender	Resources of Career Transition	No. of Persons %			
		Age Group			
		26-35 yr	36-45 yr	46-55 yr	56-65 yr
Male	Personal Contact	9	21	29	41
	Online Job Provider	44	31	17	8
	Counselor	39	28	21	12
	Organization Website	41	32	26	11
	Newspapers	21	24	26	29
Female	Personal Contact	12	22	29	37
	Online Job Provider	46	32	16	6
	Counselor	41	29	21	9
	Organization Website	43	32	24	11
	Newspapers	23	26	28	29

Chart 3: Status of Resources of Career Transition

Data table 1 show that incorporation sector no. of transition cases decrease with increasing age. For the age group 26-35 years career transition found 59% for male and 52% for female. Thus hypothesis 1, there is no significant strength of career transition cases in corporate sector in India is rejected.

Data regarding reasons of career transition indicates that salary, lack of promotion are bigger reasons while working environment, work place distance, uncomfortable feeling and managerial problems have lack effect. Therefore hypothesis 2, there is no significant reason of career transitions among working persons of corporate sector in India is rejected.

Data of table 3 shows that different available resources used by different age groups. Age group 26-35 mostly use on line job providers, websites and counselors while age group 56- 65 use personal contact. Hence hypothesis 3, there is no significant resource of career transitions among working persons in corporate sector in India is rejected.

6. Conclusion

Today, many employers are seeing the benefits of offering career transition services internally. Internal services can save company money on recruitment, training, and outplacement costs. By providing career transition services, these employers can also define their own career paths for future consideration and for the recruitment of new employees. And the career counseling they provide can not only lessen the stress of downsizing and thereby mitigate negative publicity but also train current employees for new jobs within the company.

Study shows that lack of pre knowledge of field is main reason of career transition. Most of the persons choose career on the basis of parent's desire or as follow up of other's path. Education system needs to incorporate career education since higher secondary classes. In India, career transition resources are needed to increase.

References

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